

Coumarin Derivatives—Part II : Synthesis and Screening of Some New Schiff Base Analogues of Formyl-7-Methoxycoumarin

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Manuscript received 3 May 1978, accepted 30 August 1978

A series of new Schiff base analogues derived from 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin has been synthesised and screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial, antimycobacterial, antifungal, anti-amoebic and *in vivo* anthelmintic properties.

INTERESTING biological activity has been observed in this laboratory in certain 4-[2-(heteroaryl)-vinyl] coumarins¹. We have recently reported² the synthesis and screening of various nitrones derived from 4-formyl-1-7-methoxy- and 4-hydroxy-3-formyl/acetyl-7-methoxycoumarins. In continuation of our work on synthesis and biological evaluation of coumarin derivatives, we report, in this paper the synthesis, antimicrobial and antiparasital activities of some new Schiff base analogues derived from 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin corresponding to general structures I & II.

The intermediate N-amines required for the synthesis of Schiff base analogues (I) were prepared by following the known methods³. O-Alkylhydroxylamine hydrochlorides used for preparing O-substituted oximes (II) were obtained by the condensation of acetoxime with different alkylhalides or tosylates followed by the hydrolysis of the resulting acetoxime ethers⁴.

The desired Schiff base analogues (I, Table 1) were synthesised by condensing 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin⁵ with appropriate N-amines in ethanol using acetic acid or acetic acid—sodium acetate wherever necessary. In case of two N-arylanalogues (compound nos. 1 & 2, Table-1) azeotropic removal of water formed was found necessary.

The O-substituted oximes (II, Table 2) were prepared either by condensing 4-formyl-1-7-

TABLE 1—SCHIFF BASE ANALOGUES OF 4-FORMYL-7-METHOXYCOUMARIN (I)

Sl. No.	R	Mol. Formula	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	Solvent of Crystallisation	Analysis					
						Calcd (%)			Found (%)		
						C	H	N	C	H	N
1	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NO ₃	57	186-187	DMF-EtOH	58.61	3.16	4.02	58.35	3.35	4.00
2	4-C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅ S	71	239-240	DMF-EtOH	56.98	3.91	7.82	56.45	3.50	7.96
3	-NHCONH ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄	70	228-229	iso-AmOH	55.17	4.21	16.09	54.73	4.45	16.46
4	-NHCSNH ₂	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S	56	225-226	DMF-Aq.EtOH	51.98	3.97	15.16	51.82	4.46	15.45
5	N-Morpholino	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	64	174-175	Aq.DMF	62.50	5.56	9.72	62.73	5.40	9.55
6	N-Piperidino	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	62	100-101	EtOAc- <i>n</i> -Hexane	67.13	6.29	9.79	67.53	6.45	9.54
7	N-Pyrrolidino	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	73	145-146	Aq.EtOH	66.18	5.88	10.29	65.98	6.01	10.25
8	N-Azathiacyclohexane-4,4-dioxide	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	90	248-249	DMF-EtOH	53.58	4.76	8.34	53.86	5.08	8.70
9	N-Cyclohexylamino	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	82	125-126	Aq.EtOH	68.00	6.67	9.33	67.67	6.43	9.49
10	-NHCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	80	84-86	Aq.EtOH	59.54	5.34	10.69	59.71	5.24	10.60
11	N, N'-Methylpiperazino	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃	90	124-125	EtOAc	63.78	6.31	13.94	63.52	5.88	13.91
12	N, N'-Ethoxycarbonylpiperazino	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅	77	169-170	DMF-Aq.EtOH	60.17	5.85	11.69	60.36	5.50	11.77
13	N, N'-2-Hydroxyethylpiperazino	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	60	123-124	EtOAc-Pet. Ether	61.63	6.35	12.69	61.90	6.31	12.37

methoxycoumarin with various O-alkylhydroxylamine hydrochlorides in the presence of sodium acetate or by alkylation of its oxime (I, Table 2) with appropriate alkylhalide in presence of a suitable base. All the compounds reported in Tables 1 & 2 were obtained as pale yellow to yellow crystalline solids. Their purity and homogeneity were checked by TLC and characterisation done by elemental analyses. The structures of the above Schiff bases (I) and O-substituted oximes (II) were further confirmed by their IR spectra which showed the characteristic absorption bands at 1610-1630 (C=N) and 1690-1750 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O). The NMR spectra of the representative compounds 7, 9, 11 & 12 in Table-1 and 2-4 & 10-12 in Table 2 were found consistent with assigned structures.

was refluxed and water removed azeotropically during 14 hr. The solid obtained after removal of the solvent under reduced pressure was recrystallised from DMF-EtOH to give 1, (Table 1) in fine yellow needles.

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1735 (lactone C=O) and 1630 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Compound no. 2 (Table-1) was also prepared in a similar manner.

Preparation of Semicarbazone of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (3, Table 1)

A mixture of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (1.6g, 0.0078 mol), semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.9g,

TABLE 2—O-SUBSTITUTED OXIMES OF 4-FORMYL-7-METHOXYCOUMARIN (II)

Sl. No.	R	Mol. Formula	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	Solvent of Crystallisation	Analysis					
						Calcd (%)			Found (%)		
						C	H	N	C	H	N
1	H	C ₁₁ H ₉ NO ₄	91	229-230	DMF-EtOH	60.27	4.11	6.39	60.52	3.95	6.34
2	CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ NO ₄	45	119-120	Aq. EtOH	61.80	4.72	6.00	62.16	5.46	5.81
3	C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ NO ₄	65	81-82	EtOH-EtOAc	63.16	5.26	5.67	62.90	5.38	5.56
4	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO ₄	87	81-82	Aq. EtOH	64.37	5.75	5.36	64.46	5.59	5.17
5	iso-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ NO ₄	90	69-70	Aq. EtOH	64.37	5.75	5.36	64.09	6.18	5.28
6	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO ₄	87	74-75	Aq. EtOH	65.46	6.18	5.09	65.30	5.78	4.88
7	CH ₂ C=CH	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₄	90	116-117	Aq. EtOH	65.37	4.28	5.45	65.85	4.69	5.19
8	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₄	77	80-81	Aq. EtOH	64.86	5.02	5.40	65.03	5.12	5.23
9	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ NO ₄	87	103-104	Aq. EtOH	69.90	4.85	4.53	69.63	5.20	4.87
10	CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NO ₄	77	113-114	EtOAc-Pet. Ether	59.30	4.94	5.32	59.28	4.59	5.44
11	CH ₂ CH ₂ -O-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₄	60	111-112	EtOAc	67.25	5.01	4.13	67.67	5.07	4.41
12	CH ₂ CH ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄	65	84-85	EtOAc	62.07	6.20	9.66	62.19	5.72	9.64
13	2-Pyrrolidinoethyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	45	111-112	EtOAc	64.55	6.33	8.86	64.40	5.91	8.31
14	2-Piperidinoethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄	54	59-60	EtOAc	65.46	6.65	8.49	65.40	6.35	8.41
15	2-Morpholinoethyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	65	89-90	Benzene-Pet. Ether	61.45	6.01	8.44	61.37	5.92	8.82
16	2-(4-Methylpiperazino)ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄	65	94-95	EtOAc-Pet. Ether	62.62	6.67	12.17	62.96	6.28	12.23
17	2-[4(2'-Hydroxyethyl)piperazino]ethyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	45	115-116	EtOAc	60.86	6.67	11.20	60.20	7.39	11.33

All the compounds were subjected to *in vitro* antibacterial, antimycobacterial, antifungal, anti-amoebic and *in vivo* anthelmintic screening.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open glass capillaries using Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in nujol mull or KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer and NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian A 90 (model EM-390) instrument using TMS as internal standard.

Preparation of 4-(2,4-dichlorophenyliminomethyl)-7-methoxycoumarin (1, Table-1)

A mixture of 2,4-dichloroaniline (2.63g, 0.016 mol) and 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (2.04g, 0.01 mol) in dry DMF (100 ml) and benzene (50 ml)

0.0078 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.7g, 0.0078 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. The solvent was removed and the resulting product recrystallised from *iso*-AmOH to give 3 as yellow fine crystalline solid. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3410, 3300 (NH₂), 1700 (lactone C=O) and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Thiosemicarbazone (4, Table 1) was obtained in a similar manner excepting that sodium acetate was not required during the reaction.

Preparation of 4-(N-morpholinoiminomethyl)-7-methoxycoumarin (5, Table 1)

A solution of N-aminomorpholine (2.04 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (3.05 g,

0.015 ml) in ethanol (300 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (4-6 drops) and saturated aqueous sodium acetate solution (5 ml) maintaining the temperature at 0-10°. The reaction mixture was kept at 10° for 1 hr and left overnight at room temperature. The solvent was removed completely under reduced pressure and the residue was neutralised with aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous DMF to give **5** as fine yellow needles: ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1760 (lactone C=O) and 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N). NMR (CDCl_3) δ 3.28 (t, $J=6\text{Hz}$, 4H, $-(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{N}-$), 3.95 (t, $J=6\text{Hz}$, 4H, $-(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{O}-$), 3.80 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 6.58-6.80 (m, 2H, H_a & H_b), 7.42 (s, 1H, CH=N) and 8.25 (d, $J_{5,6}=9\text{Hz}$, 1H, H_5).

Compound nos. **6-13**, Table 1 were synthesised in the same way.

Preparation of the oxime of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (1, Table 2) Method A

A solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (5.56 g, 0.08 mol) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (16.32 g, 0.08 mol) in ethanol (500 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (170 ml) and saturated aqueous sodium acetate (6.56 g, 0.08 mol) maintaining the temperature at 0°. The product started separating out after 30 min. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 16 hr. and diluted with water (2 litres). The resulting solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water, dried and recrystallised from DMF-EtOH to give the title compound as pale yellow fibrous needles. ν_{\max}^{KBr} 3200 (OH), 1700 (lactone C=O) and 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N). NMR (TFA): 3.65 (s, 1H, OH, exchangeable with D_2O), 3.65 (s, 3H, OCH_3 , merged with OH), 6.32 (s, 1H, H_a), 6.60-6.85 (m, 2H, H_b & H_c), 7.60 (d, $J_{5,6}=9\text{Hz}$, H_5) and 8.25 (s, 1H, CH=N).

O-Alkyloximes nos. **3**, **10**, **11**, **13** and **15-17** in Table 2 were prepared by method A excepting that acetic acid was not necessary in the reaction mixture.

Preparation of O-methyloxime of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (2, Table 2) Method B

To a stirred solution of compound no. **1**, Table 2 (4.38 g, 0.02 mol) in methanol (150 ml) containing freshly prepared sodium methoxide (1.35 g, 0.025 mol), was added methyl iodide (3.55 g, 0.025 mol) and stirring was continued for further 45 min. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way to give compound **2** as pale yellow needles, identical with the compound obtained by method A. ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1725 (lactone C=O) and 1615 cm^{-1} (C=N),

NMR (TFA): δ 4.00 (s, 3H, 7- OCH_3), 4.20 (s, 3H, N- OCH_3), 6.70 (s, 1H, H_a), 6.90-7.20 (m, 2H, H_b & H_c), 8.25 (d, $J_{5,6}=9\text{Hz}$, 1H, H_5) and 8.40 (s, 1H, CH=N).

Compound nos. **3** and **4-9** in Table 2 were prepared by following method B.

Preparation of O(-2-N, N-dimethylaminoethyl) oxime of 4-formyl-7-methoxycoumarin (12, Table 2)

To a suspension of 2-N, N-dimethylaminoethyl-chloride hydrochloride (4.32 g, 0.03 mol) in dry toluene (50 ml) containing dry sodium methoxide (1.62 g, 0.03 mol) was added slowly, a suspension of dry sodium salt of compound **1**, Table 2 (7.23 g, 0.03 mol) in dry toluene (100 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed in an oil bath for 4 hr with stirring and worked up in the usual way to give the title compound as light yellow crystalline solid.

ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1725 (lactone C=O) and 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N).

NMR (TFA); δ 3.14-3.30 (two singlets, 6H, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}-$), 3.60-3.88 (m, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}-$), 4.00 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 4.68-4.85 (m, 2H, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$), 6.80 (s, 1H, H_a), 6.95-7.25 (m, 2H, H_b & H_c), 8.10 (d, $J_{5,6}=9\text{Hz}$, 1H, H_5) and 8.40 (s, 1H, CH=N).

Compound no. **14** (Table 2) was also prepared in a similar manner.

Results and Discussion

Biological Screening

All the compounds reported in Tables 1 & 2 were tested for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity by serial dilution tube method and antifungal activity by agar dilution assay method as described earlier⁶. The highest dilution of the test compound which inhibited the visual growth of the organism was taken as the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC, $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The bacteria employed were *S. aureus*, *S. faecalis*, *E. coli*, *Ps. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, *S. typhi*, *A. tumefaciens*, *P. vulgaris*, *V. cholerae* and *S. dysenteriae*, *M. tuberculosis* H_{37}Rv . The fungi used were *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum*, *M. canis*, *M. gypseum*, *C. albicans*, *Cr. neoformans*, *A. fumigatus*, *H. capsulatum*, *S. schenckii* and *E. floccosum*. The *in vitro* anti-amoebic activity of the compounds against *E. histolytica* was determined by standard procedure⁷. The compounds were also screened for their *in vivo* anthelmintic activity against *N. dubius*, *N. brasiliensis* and *H. nana* in rats following the known methods⁸.

The *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activities of all compounds tested were insignificant although several Schiff bases and O-substituted oximes were found to possess weak antituberculosis activity at 100-200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. N-cyclohexyl hydrazone (compound **9**, Table-1) exhibited highest activity against

M. tuberculosis H₃₇Rv by inhibiting its growth at 25 µg/ml).

Three hydrazones (compound nos. 11-13, Table 1) and three O-substituted oximes (compound nos. 11, 14 & 16, Table 2) showed appreciable *in vitro* anti-amoebic activity against *E. histolytica* at 62.5-125 µg/ml while the remaining were inactive. The *in vivo* anthelmintic activity of all the compounds at 250 mg/kg×3 days were insignificant. However, two O-substituted oximes (compound nos. 4 & 5, Table 2) should 37-42% inhibition against *N. brasiliensis* at the same dose level but were inactive against *N. dubius* and *H. nana*.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Drs. G.S. Reddi, K. K. Bhopale and staff of biology division of this department for biological screening. Thanks are also due to the staff of our analytical laboratories for elemental analyses and spectral data.

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